

ORGANIZATION OF INTERACTION BETWEEN DIDACTIC AND EDUCATIONAL AND DEVELOPMENTAL INTENTIONS IN THE ORGANIZATION OF THE MODERN EDUCATIONAL PROCESS ACCORDING TO THE METHODS OF RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AND MODERN RUSSIAN LITERARY LANGUAGE

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Annotation .

This article addresses the current problems of using audiovisual methods and means to fulfill the developmental and educational goals of a Russian language lesson at school, as well as organizing the interaction of didactic and educational and developmental intentions in the organization of the modern educational process using the methods of Russian as a foreign language and modern Russian literary language.

Key words: lesson, method, audiovisual means, technology analysis, discipline, ethics, teacher, recipient.

In recent years, in our Republic, using modern methods and means with the participation of foreign experts and experienced teachers, a national general education program has been developed, which is being tested in research and educational institutions of Uzbekistan. Also, experimental testing of basic Russian language textbooks, teaching aids and their examination by Uzbek and foreign specialists from the Russian Federation began. Today, in the situation of modern modernization of public education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, special attention is given to the problem of assessing the quality of teaching academic disciplines. In particular, in relation to the possibility of transitioning the teaching of the Russian language in secondary schools from the SRFL (RKR) methodology to the RFL methodology (Russian as a foreign language).

Note that it is absolutely not necessary to subordinate every Russian language lesson to an educational task. This is extremely difficult to do, unlike a Russian literature lesson, where the analysis of the moral, ethical and philosophical issues of a work of art itself includes an educational function. However, it is still necessary to strive for this task. You should not think that it is generally impossible to implement an educational task within the framework of a Russian language lesson, and we will show how this can be done specifically using the following examples.

First, we take for analysis the poem by Vladimir Mayakovsky "What is good and what is bad", we carry out an expert assessment of it for compliance with didactic requirements and the level of language competence of children. We select a class and a suitable topic for the lesson (for example, "studying Russian verbs, adjectives, coordinating them with nouns in numbers, persons and cases").

After the preparatory activities, we begin the lesson, present its didactic part, and move on to consolidating the material in the form of doing exercises . To do this, together with the children, we read and translate the text of the poem, and then ask the students the simplest and most unpretentious question: which human actions are good and which are bad? The

answers received are arranged in the form of a table, written by the teacher on the blackboard (as we can see, this does not require particularly complex and expensive means at all).

It is important to take into account the connection between the educational goal and the didactic goal, where we need to explain the features of the adverb as an independent part of speech, paying special attention to the fact that it is the adverb that allows us to express the author's assessment of the situation reflected in the language. In this case, for this, the author of the poem uses the words "good" and "bad" as moral categories, summing up the description of the behavior of certain children.

Understanding the complexity of the educational process involved in Russian language lessons, especially its emotional and irrational nature, it is very important to teach our children discipline and silence during the lesson so as not to disturb their classmates.

Therefore, for educational purposes of instilling discipline, complicated homework should be given, not from the point of view of qualitative, but from the point of view of quantitative labor intensity. For example, in addition to the usual exercise, force students to memorize a poem in Russian, constantly increasing its text volume. To begin with, you can use short poems by O. Khayyam:

Silence is a shield from many troubles
And chatter is always harmful.
A person's tongue is small
But he ruined many lives.

Then you can move on to Tyutchev's poetry " Silentium " or other prose texts of the classics. In addition, when performing Russian language exercises in class, schoolchildren must be placed in conditions where academic performance will directly depend on compliance with discipline and silence. To do this, the class is divided into two or three groups depending on the number of rows of desks, and for competition, two or three leaders are delegated to the board. One writes Russian words on the topic "Vegetables" on the right side of the board, the other "Fruits". The one who writes the most Russian words from memory without mistakes gets a good grade.

It is especially important when determining the rules of the game to establish a mandatory condition: with any hints and shouts from the seat, all points scored must be canceled, and the student called to the board receives a C instead of an A or B. Only the row whose representatives observe the established order and silence wins the competition. This is how children are taught collective responsibility and discipline.

Now let's see how, using the example of drawing up a plan for a specific lesson, we can implement educational and developmental tasks in teaching the Russian language. For example, take the topic: "Studying perfective and imperfective verbs."

In the first part of the plan, we formulate the goals and objectives of the lesson. They consist in the implementation of the following competencies necessary to work on the following problematic issues that the teacher poses to children :

"1. Educational (didactic) competence.

What is the difference between perfective and imperfective verbs in Russian ? How do prefixes indicate the formation of perfective and imperfective forms?

2. General subject competence.

What have you learned about the natural world of the Altai Mountains? What animals live there and what kind of relationships develop between these animals?

3. Educational competence

Compare behavior in the animal world with the human world. Have you ever encountered a situation where someone strong offended a weak person? How did this conflict end? Did he have a fair solution to the problem?"

Developmental competence does not contain issues discussed in the lesson, so it is simply written down in the lesson plan as follows:

"4. Developmental competence is necessary to develop interest in learning the Russian language."

Then we write down the teaching methods:

"Teaching methods: grammatical-translation, conscious-practical, audiolingual , audiovisual" - and we write what they mean:

"These methods include:

- Presentation of didactic material using video materials to implement the principles of clarity and awareness.*
- Formation of student activity and interest in the subject being studied*
- Conducting a heuristic conversation with schoolchildren on linguistic, moral, ethical and cultural topics to implement the principle of problem-solving using interdisciplinary connections in Russian language lessons."*

We indicate the material teaching aids that we have available: instead of a smart board, it can be handouts, a textbook, etc. depending on the capabilities of the technical equipment of the educational institution.

"Teaching tools: smart board, laptop, audio materials, video materials."

After this, we move on to the description of the main part of the lesson with a description of the actions of the students and the actions of the teacher, which is not provided for in the practice of drawing up lesson plans in our schools, but is widely used in modern international standards.

At the same time, the position of the teacher in dialogue with school youth is also problematic because he recognizes himself as a representative of that huge information space of culture that stands behind him and does not always strive to stick out his "self" in front of the recipient, believing that flaunting individual shades opinions on any scientific problem is purely ethically incorrect. According to M. Weber, "the better the teacher fulfills his task, the more conscientiously he avoids instilling in his listeners his position, his point of view ¹." In a sense, he becomes a medium between the system of science and culture that is contained in his consciousness and the perceiving consciousness of the listener himself.

In the Bakhtinian model of dialogue, the dialogical relationship for each of the subjects of the dialogue is a combination of an altruistic intention of understanding the other with a personalized growth of individual self-awareness, the initiator of which is the position of the "other".

¹ Weber M. Science as a calling and profession // Selected works. M. 1990. P. 722. P. 722.

Of course, the impulse of self-awareness can be present in the dialogue, but it would be better if it were hidden as much as possible within the implementation of any pedagogical technology. Otherwise, an illusion arises of adapting the audience "to oneself," while in reality the teacher is trying not so much to close the dialogue on himself, but to introduce the student's consciousness into the system of knowledge that is transmitted by the teacher in the educational process.

Therefore, the most effective system for establishing dialogic relationships between the student and teaching environment can be the implementation of only this model: "I am for them, and they are for me."

The emotional impression on which the audiovisual method of teaching the Russian language is based is irrational and unformalizable. This means that quality control of teaching the Russian language should be inseparable from moral control, since these forms of supervision are internally interrelated.

At the same time, in order to engage in moral control (that is, to monitor the results of educational work with children in terms of discipline and the nature of the actions they commit), you need to be able to work with personnel, know the people working in the education system, their character and characteristics of irrational thinking - and Artificial intelligence will not be able to carry out this operation. Therefore, to manage people, a teacher is needed who has not only rational, but also irrational conscious competence, based on high moral levels.

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